

SOME STRUCTURAL PROPERTIES OF

CERAMIC MATRIX FIBER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The tensile and shear properties of ceramic matrix fiber composites are described and microstructures that provide optimum structural properties identified. A transition in the axial tensile fracture mechanism is elucidated and used to place bounds on the microstructural parameters needed to achieve good tensile properties. The related compromise in shear strength and transverse tensile properties is also assessed. Such considerations reveal that high matrix toughness, and fiber strength and modulus are generally desirable. However, an ability to adjust the interfacial frictional resistance between the fiber and matrix is an essential requirement for effective microstructural design.

1. Introduction

Ceramic matrix fiber composites have been shown to exhibit damage tolerant axial tensile characteristics (1-3), when the bond between fiber and matrix is frictional and the fiber strengths are high (3). The axial tensile response of such composites is characterized by (fig. 1) periodic matrix cracking (3,4) occurring at a stress σ_0 . Such cracking is followed by fiber bundle failure, at an ultimate tensile strength σ_u , and then, fiber pull-out, supported by the interfacial frictional resistance τ . None of these characteristic stresses (σ_0 , σ_u and τ) are sensitive to matrix damage, because the fibers have sufficient failure strength to support the load in the presence of arbitrary matrix cracking. Such damage tolerant tensile behavior is regarded as advantageous for the tensile structural performance of ceramic matrix composites. However, transitions to less desirable tensile behavior and inferior shear characteristics are potential structural problems.

Axial tensile properties are degraded when the matrix cracking event is accompanied by fiber failure, resulting in relatively short fiber pull-out lengths (6) (fig. 2). The transition to simultaneous fiber failure occurs as the level of bonding (chemical or frictional) between fiber and matrix increases. The nature of this transition in behavior is evaluated in this paper. Furthermore, the important tensile properties, such as the fracture toughness, are described and related to the fiber/matrix bonding characteristics and other microstructural properties.

Premature shear failure (fig. 3) constitutes an important limitation of ceramic matrix fiber composites (5,6). A loss in shear strength invariably accompanies the incorporation of fibers into a ceramic matrix, because of shear stress concentrations in the matrix induced by the fibers (6). An analysis of this problem is presented, as required to define microstructures that provide an optimum combination of the tensile and shear characteristics required for structural purposes.

2. Axial Tensile Properties

2.1 Fracture Mechanisms

The stress/strain behavior of a ceramic matrix fiber composite is primarily dictated by a combination of the shear resistance of the fiber/matrix interface and the propensity for fiber fracture. When the fibers remain intact as the matrix crack propagates, a steady state condition is established for long cracks (4,7-10) whereby the matrix cracking stress σ_0 becomes independent of crack length, a (fig. 4a) (4,7,8),

$$\sigma_0 \equiv \sigma_a + \sigma_R = \left[\frac{6(1-\nu^2)K_0^2 \tau E_f f^2 (1-f)(1+\eta)^2}{E_m R} \right]^{1/3} \quad (1)$$

where R is the fiber radius, K_0 is the matrix toughness, E is Young's modulus (with subscripts m and f referring to the matrix and fiber), ν is Poisson's ratio, f is the area fraction of fibers along the fracture plane, σ_a is the applied stress required for matrix cracking, σ_R is the axial residual stress in the matrix, and $\eta = E_f f / E_m (1-f)$. The steady-state characteristic emerges because the intact fibers in the crack wake place an upper limit on the crack opening, corresponding to the equilibrium separation (9,10) of the completely failed matrix (fig. 4b) (dictated by τ , f and the applied loads). Consequently, only a small near-tip segment

Figure 1 - A schematic axial tensile stress-strain curve for an ideal ceramic matrix composite indicating the associated damage events.

Figure 2 - A scanning electron micrograph of the fiber pull-out when fiber fracture accompanies matrix cracking.

Figure 3 - A scanning electron micrograph of a shear crack, indicating the ejected matrix between intact fibers.

Figure 4a - The effect of crack length on the matrix cracking stress when fibers remain intact in the wake.

of the crack, a_0 , wherein the crack opening is less than the limiting value, influences the matrix stress intensity. The length of this segment is given by (8)

$$a_0 \approx 1.2 \left[\frac{K_o(1-f)(1+\eta)R}{\tau f \eta (1-\nu^2)} \right]^{2/3} \quad (2)$$

Alternatively, for short cracks ($a < a_0$) the matrix strength σ_m exceeds σ_o and becomes crack length dependent (8), as depicted in fig. 4a. Nevertheless, provided that σ_m is less than the fiber bundle strength, the composite still exhibits desirable tensile load bearing capability beyond the advent of non-linearity (fig. 5).

Changes in the frictional resistance τ or in fiber strength S may result in fiber failure in the wake (fig. 6) as the matrix crack propagates. Then, the matrix cracking stress, σ_o , is fully crack length dependent and coincides with the ultimate tensile strength (fig. 6). With this change in fracture mechanism the fracture toughness of the composite, K_c , becomes the important material parameter. The strength of the composite is given by

$$\sigma \sim K_c a^{-1/2} \quad (3)$$

and the toughness, is given by (9);

$$K_c = K_o [1 + 2(Sf/\sigma_o)^3] (E/E_m) \quad (4)$$

The toughness increases as the fiber bundle strength increases, and as the interfacial frictional resistance (and hence, σ_o) decreases, because such changes increase the extent of the fiber bridging zone, D , in the crack wake.

The transition between intact and failing fibers is dictated by the relative values of the steady-state matrix cracking stress, σ_o , and the fiber fracture stress, S . Steady state crack growth in the long crack limit ($a \gg a_0, D$) requires that σ_o be less than Sf . Thereupon, provided that the fibers are initially intact, steady state is established without fiber failure. Consequently, the criterion $\sigma_o < Sf$ (eqn 1) yields a transition inequality, T , given by;

$$\frac{\tau K_o^2 (1-f)^2 (1-\nu^2) \eta (1+\eta)^2}{S^3 f^2 R} \equiv T < 0.1 \quad (5)$$

Steady-state behavior is thus encouraged by small values of $\tau K_m^2 / RS^3$. For short cracks ($a \approx a_0, D$) the transition is more complex and is not given explicit consideration in this article.

2.2 Experimental Measurements

Tensile tests, conducted on an LAS glass ceramic uniaxially reinforced with 50% SiC fibers, reveal a transition in fracture behavior with temperature. At room temperature, the fibers remain intact during matrix fracture and the stress-strain curve has the form depicted in fig. 1 (3). At this temperature, independent measurements of τ (2MPa) (3) and S (2 GPa)

Figure 4b - An optical micrograph of an equilibrium crack opening in the presence of intact fibers.

Figure 5 - A schematic trend in the tensile stress-strain curve, upon changes in the crack length, a , compared with the equilibrium length, a_0 .

indicate that $T = 3 \times 10^{-3}$ for this composite ($f = 0.5$, $K_0 = 2 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$, $E_m = 85 \text{ GPa}$, $E_f = 200 \text{ GPa}$, $R = 8 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$). Thus, steady state cracking is predicted from eqn (5), consistent with the observed stress-strain behavior. Furthermore, the measured matrix cracking stress ($\sim 290 \pm 20 \text{ MPa}$) is consistent with the value predicted from eqn (1) ($\sigma_0 = 307 \text{ MPa}$) with $\sigma_R = 0$ and the above microstructural parameters.

At 1000C fiber fracture accompanies matrix cracking, resulting in a stress-strain curve similar to fig. 6. Independent measurements of τ (20MPa) and S (1 GPa) give $T \approx 10^{-1}$. This value of T just exceeds the transition magnitude (eqn 5) and is thus again consistent with the observed stress, strain behavior. Additionally, the measured toughness ($K_C = 5 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$) is reasonably predicted by eqn (4), ($K_C \approx 4 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$),

On the basis of these results, it is tentatively concluded that a major transition in fracture behavior in fiber reinforced ceramic matrix composites can be predicted, based primarily on the magnitudes of the fiber strength S and the interfacial shear resistance between fiber and matrix, τ . Furthermore, the matrix cracking stress in the intact fiber regime and the fracture toughness in the fiber failure regime are adequately predicted from independent measurements of S and τ . However, it is also recognised that another failure mode, involving fiber failure ahead of the matrix crack, is possible. The transition to this failure mode is not well understood presently, but involves considerations of fiber debonding ahead of the crack, as discussed in the following section.

2.3 Optimum Microstructures

The axial tensile properties of ceramic matrix fiber composites are dictated by the interfacial shear resistance, τ , and hence the nature of the bond between the fiber and matrix. Successfully processed composites (1,2) appear to have no chemical bond (3) and thus, no resistance to the opening of the interface ahead of the crack. Consequently, the matrix crack does not create singular stresses within the fibers. Instead the fibers are subject to a moderate, uniform tension along the separated length (7) and the tendency for fiber failure ahead of the crack is thereby minimized. For composites of this type, τ derives from frictional effects that oppose the relative displacements of the fibers and matrix in the wake of the crack (significant interfacial separation forces do not exist in the wake). The analysis in the previous section is thus deemed most applicable to composites with frictional bonding. When chemical bonding occurs between fiber and matrix, the extent of debonding ahead of the crack dictates the tendency for frontal fiber failure. A comprehensive understanding of the behavior of chemically bonded ceramic composites is not presently available. However, initial calculations (7) reveal that very small values of the interfacial failure resistance (c.f. the matrix toughness) are needed to achieve significant debonding and, hence, to allow fiber failure sufficiently remote from the crack plane to allow brittle, ceramic fibers to contribute appreciably to the toughness (by pull-out work in the wake (9)). It is thus considered unlikely that ceramic composites having interfacial bonding stronger than perhaps Van der Waals forces would exhibit good tensile properties (fig. 1).

With the preceding restrictions on bonding, the values of S , f and τ required to achieve desirable tensile properties are fully expressed by eqn (5). Consequently, with a specified and limited range of matrix and fiber characteristics (S , K_0 , E_f , E_m), τ and f can, in principle, be adjusted to give steady-state cracking behavior. However, independent control of τ is not readily achieved, because of thermal expansion differences between

Figure 6 - A schematic indicating trends in the stress strain curve with crack length and toughness when fiber failure occurs in the wake.

Figure 7 - A scanning electron micrograph of matrix microcracks within a region subject to in-plane shear stress.

fiber and matrix and the requirement that chemical bonding be averted at the interface. Furthermore, τ and σ_R are undoubtedly interrelated(7).

3. Shear Properties

Regions of a composite subject to shear stresses are susceptible to matrix microcracking (fig. 7) and associated shear failure (6) (fig. 3). The incidence of microcracking and the magnitude of the shear strength is apparently influenced by shear stress concentrations in the matrix, between fiber bundles (6,10) (fig. 8). Furthermore, for typical ceramic composites, the stress concentrations are larger when the fibers are not chemically bonded to the matrix. Consequently, the shear strength of the matrix is degraded by incorporating a large volume fraction of unbonded fibers. For this case, preliminary analysis of microcrack coalescence and the associated strain energy changes (fig. 9) indicates a shear strength (6),

$$\tau_s \approx \frac{K_o f^{1/4} (1-f)}{R^{1/2} (1+f) (1+v)} \quad (6)$$

The specific trends in τ_s revealed by eqn (6) are deemed reasonable. Notably, increased resistance to matrix microcracking derives from an increase in K_o and a decrease in matrix stress concentration between fiber bundles as f decreases. However, the specific magnitude of τ_s is not regarded as accurate because the heterogeneity of the fiber distribution (which influences the stress concentration) is not explicitly included in the analysis.

4. Property Compromises

Present evidence indicates that unique axial tensile properties (fig. 1) can be achieved in ceramic composites by incorporating strong fibers that do not bond chemically to the matrix. Furthermore, by controlling the frictional resistance at the interface and the volume fraction of fibers (subject to specified magnitudes of fiber strength, matrix toughness and elastic moduli of fiber and matrix) the stress-strain characteristics can be tailored to specific application requirements. However, the thermal expansion differences between fiber and matrix, which are intimately involved in determining the interfacial frictional resistance, also produce residual stresses. The residual stresses exert an important influence on the tensile properties, and must be fully considered. In fact, an optimum thermal expansion difference can be predicted (7).

Good axial tensile properties are necessarily achieved at the expense of diminished shear and transverse tensile properties, because of the required absence of bonding. Nevertheless, a general improvement in tensile and shear properties can be attained by selecting a matrix with high toughness, provided that the interfacial shear resistance can be adjusted to inhibit fiber failure in the wake of the matrix crack (eqn 5). Additionally, the choice of high strength and high modulus fibers has the advantage that good axial tensile properties are feasible with a minimum volume fraction of fibers and the consequent minimal degradation of the shear and transverse tensile properties. Finally, it is noted that fibers with the smallest diameter amenable to composite processing are generally desirable.

Figure 8 - The effects of elastic modulus mismatch upon shear stress concentration between fiber bundles.

Figure 9 - A schematic of the mechanism of propagation of a shear crack in a fiber composite.

5. Concluding Remarks

The preceding summary of tensile and shear properties exhibited by uniaxially reinforced ceramic fiber composites provides a preliminary framework for the design and analysis of such materials. Emphasis has been placed on the role of various properties of the fibers, matrix and interface, such that optimal microstructures can be created for specific mechanical property requirements. However, additional experimental study, particularly of the transitions in mechanism proposed in this article, are clearly required to substantiate fully the present approach. Furthermore, extension of the research to biaxially reinforced composites may reveal additional failure mechanisms.

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